

W-STEM: Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM

598923-EPP-1-2018-1-ES-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Guidelines for Conducting Interviews

W-STEM App Development Team

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Author	Modification	DOI
1	0	10/10/2019	ITESM	Initial version	
1	0	14/11/2019	USAL	Review and testing the protocol	
1	1	10/01/2020	ITESM	Minor changes	
1	2	23/01/2020	ITESM	Minor changes	
1	3	23/01/2020	TUD	Revision and minor changes	
1	4	12/02/2020	TUD	Revision and minor changes	
2	0	12/02/2020	ITESM	Inclusion of the consent form	
3	0	10/07/2022	USAL	Final review	10.5281/zenodo.6815936
3	1	10/07/2022	USAL	Corrigendum	10.5281/zenodo.6816253

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Introduction

The W-STEM project [1-19] requires that all partners record 25 interviews with role models of women in STEM. This document contains guidelines that you must use to record these interviews. **Note that editing should not be undertaken until editing guidelines have been provided.** This will be discussed in our online meetings and will be one of the areas of focus for the face-to-face meeting in Dublin (this meeting was developed online due to the COVID-19 [20-23]).

Videos should be good quality, but it is equally important that we have a consistent style across all 375 (25 videos * 15 partners) videos. Therefore, these guidelines provided must be followed.

A sample, completed video is available https://youtu.be/bVHs_CDGO_g.

Guideline 1: Make a Plan

All partners should have recorded the majority of (or ideally **all**) their videos in advance of the meeting in Dublin on 7-8 May. All videos will need to have been recorded and edited before the end of June.

Guideline 2: Recruit Interviewees

Each partner is required to record 25 interviews with women role models in STEM. These should be a mix of women in different professions and at different stages of their career. This can include, for example, women in senior / C-suite positions in companies, professors in academia, early and mid-career professionals, recent graduates pursuing research careers in academia and others.

Guideline 3: Be aware of the objective of the video

The objective of the W-STEM project is to attract, guide and increase the access of women around the world to science, technology, engineering and mathematics. The videos will be shared on social media, so once they are edited, they will be **2-3 minutes** in length. It is important to guide interviewees to keep their responses brief, focused and engaging.

Guideline 4: Organize your technology

For your video to be accepted, it must meet the following specifications:

- 720p (1280×720 px; also called HD ready or standard HD).
- Landscape format (shot that is composed horizontally).
- The video must have adequate audio and, if possible, use a microphone to avoid external or background noise whether you record with a cell phone or video camera.
- Look for image stability, use a tripod or base for the recording device.
- When filming is best to stick to record at 24 or 30fps or frames per second.
- The video format must be MP4, MPEG, MOV, FLV or AVI.

Recording on a typical smart phone, with a good camera quality, should be sufficient to meet these requirements.

Guideline 5: Write a Script

Select appropriate questions from the interview protocol for your interviewee. You do not need to cover all questions in the Interview Protocol. If possible, provide the script to the interviewee in advance so that they can plan their (brief but focused and engaging) responses.

Interview Protocol

- 1) **Brief introduction.** Ask interviewee to introduce herself.
- 2) **Career.** In this section of the interview we aim to know what motivated the interviewee in their decision-making process. This section is directed for students and professionals alike.
Suggested questions: a) *Why did you choose your STEM field?*, b) *Were you inspired by someone or something?*
- 3) **Current occupation.** In this section of the interview we aim to know the interviewee's experience in their field. This section is directed for professionals only.
Suggested questions: c) *Which topic are you working on at the moment?*, d) *What is exciting about your job?*, e) *What are you passionate about? / What do you like?*
- 4) **Future plans.** In this section of the interview we aim to know how they see themselves as professionals in STEM in the future. This section is directed for students and professionals alike.
Suggested questions: f) *How do you think you'll make a difference?*, g) *In ten years, what do you hope to have accomplished in terms of your work?*
- 5) **Inspiration for women in science.** In this section we aim to know the interviewees' opinions and motivational insights as women in a STEM field.
Suggested questions: h) *Why is it important that more women pursue STEM education*, i) *If you had the option to give advice to a younger version of yourself, what would that be?*, j) *What inspirational message would you give young girls to inspire them to pursue STEM?*

Guideline 6: Select a Location

If possible, look for a place with natural light or suitable artificial lights. Take care of background noise so that the interviewee's voice can be clearly heard.

Guideline 7: Get the interviewee's consent

Ensure that the interviewee signs the consent form included on page 7 of this document. This ensures that the interviewee understands that their video will be shared online.

Guideline 8: Agree with the interviewee how they will appear

Another relevant aspect is the camera shots for your video. The shots are the different ways of recording with a camera that help us transmit various ideas, impressions and emotions. For these videos, interviewed person would be the only person on the scene, so you should consider the shot for its appearance. In the final video, it is expected that only the interviewee will make appearance, meaning that the frames when the interviewer speaks will be trimmed and the questions will appear in the video as text on screen. Close up shot show only a person's face or face and shoulders and are intended to convey emotions or reactions. Medium Close Up shows the character in the middle, usually from the waist or hip up and serve to show actions and put ourselves in context, but still paying attention to the character. Wide shot shows people, actions or complete places, like a person walking. The intention of the shot is to place ourselves in a place, in order to give us an idea of where the story unfolds.

Guideline 9: Have your script at hand

Bring the script with the selected questions from the protocol, to review them before the recording. You can use mobile devices as a mean to display the script during the scene. This way you can ask off-stage questions at the right time.

Guideline 10: Record Separate Clips per Segment

When your script is ready, we suggest dividing it into small scenes (30-45 seconds max), that is separate video clips that when edited together will be part of the final video. This will make recording easier, as if you need to re-record one of the scenes, you will only do as necessary. It is possible that there is an opportunity to unexpectedly interview a person in conferences or talks, so it will be advisable to always have at hand the basic structure of the interview protocol.

Guideline 11: Edit

Please **do not start editing the videos yet**. Guidelines will be provided for editing, and tutorials will be offered to help guide people. This will also be a focus of the online meetings and at the meeting in Dublin in 7-8 May.

Editing must ensure a consistent presentation of all video content.

LETTER OF CONSENT TO BE PHOTOGRAPHED OR RECORDED IN VIDEO AND/OR AUDIO FORMAT

In accordance with the data protection laws, it is our duty to obtain your articulate consent to participate in the project **W-STEM** (Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM), funded under European Union ERASMUS+ Capacity-building in Higher Education Programme (598923-EPP-1-2018-1-ES-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP). Therefore, to participate consciously, you are hereby informed that:

Any personal information that you provide will be kept by the coordination of **W-STEM**. Your information is obtained to participate in the **W-STEM** project, which has the purpose of encouraging the participation of women in STEM.

You hereby consent to the free cession of rights of image, voice, video, and particularly reproduction, distribution and public communication (including the transformation and diffusion through the internet), for the media and support that **W-STEM** deems appropriate. Under no concept will they be commercialized; in any case they will be distributed for free and with divulgatory objectives of **W-STEM**.

This cession will allow the exhibition of the provided material (photography, audio and/or video), always within the framework of **W-STEM**. Furthermore, the person who signs guarantees that they are legitimate owner of the rights of image and that they have obtained the rights on any third-party content or images. The European Commission support for the production of audiovisual materials does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

We also inform you that you can opt out of the project, deny access, or cancel the use of your information at any given moment through direct and written communication, by sending a message through our website: wstemproject.eu/contact/. The fact of sending a video implies the recognition that the information and personal data that you provide are yours, exact and true.

By signing this consent letter, I _____
authorize **W-STEM** to use photos, videos or audio recordings without previous notice and express approval. I have read this letter of consent carefully and fully comprehend its meaning and implications.

Signature

Date

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